

The Study of Scheduled Caste Movement and Protest in Western Uttar Pradesh

Author's Details:

- ⁽¹⁾ **Dr. Krishna Agrawal**, Associate Professor, Head of Department of Sociology, S.V. College, Aligarh
⁽²⁾ **Dr. Abhimanyu kumar**, Head of Department of Sociology Govt. P.G. College, Ranikhet, Almora

Abstract

The term 'Scheduled Castes' is used for 'untouchables' as the then British colonial government through its Government of India Act 1935 placed these people in a schedule. In 1936, the British Government of India Order included certain castes in the list of Depressed Classes, such as the Scheduled Caste people. The Scheduled Caste people are in the lowest rung in the caste hierarchy throughout the country of India. In this social order of uneven relationships, the Scheduled Caste people are at the underside; and therefore are thought to be generally substandard to all others in the Indian community. This paper is based on the secondary sources related to scheduled caste movement

Keywords: - Scheduled caste, people, community and relationship

Introduction: - As stated in the Introduction to the Thesis, the Government of India Act 1935 was an important landmark in the history of the legal place of the Scheduled Caste people of India as the ex-untouchables were placed in a 'schedule' according to the Government of India Act, 1935; and according to it, the ex-untouchables were for the first time termed as Scheduled Castes. In 1936, it is believed that the colonial British Government of India ordered in specifying certain castes in the list of Depressed Classes as Scheduled Castes. The Scheduled Caste people traditionally occupied the lowly ranks in the hierarchy of caste in the Indian Hindu society. In the social order of this relationship which was unequal in nature, the Scheduled Caste people are at the underside and therefore they were thought to be the most socially substandard to all others in the Hindu communal order. The Scheduled Castes were thought to be one of the castes which had been the most backward both socially and economically. The basic determinants of who can be termed as belonging to Scheduled Caste were untouchability, impure occupations, very low economic, political and educational status.

After independence, the Scheduled Caste people were given special mention by Dr. Bhim Rao Ambedkar in the Constitution of India which provides them with the special provisions for their education, employment, and political representation. Article 46 of the Constitution of India, for instance, declares. "The state shall promote with special care the programmers for educational and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people and in particular of the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes and shall protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitation" (Wankhede, 1999: 28).

SCHEDULED CASTE MOVEMENT AND PROTEST IN WESTERN U.P.

Meaning of Protest:

A protest can be usually be viewed as an attack on the system which has something wrong with it against which people will be protesting in an organized and as well as often in an intellectual way. From this point of view, it can be said that a protest points out that there is certain sickness in the society which needs to be removed or uprooted and a protest exactly tries to do that. It tries to break down the erstwhile social order, and civil war protest is thought to be based on every man's desire to be free from the clutches of suffering and oppression. This feeling is above any reason, tradition, and power. A protest may be rather good or bad, but it is thought to be an effective way through which social change and mobility in modern society can be achieved. Most of the political and social change of the 20th century has been accelerated by various protest movements that have happened.

The Scheduled Castes Movement and Protests in U.P.: Some Evidence:-

The S.C./Dalit Movement in U.P. has specific characteristics which distinguish it from the Ambedkar movements in other regions, especially Maharashtra. The Dalit Movement in U.P. arose later than in Western and Southern India, and in the colonial period, it was both weak and limited to a few pockets of the state. The absence of anti-caste social movements and the moderating effects of Gandhi upon the anti-colonial struggle shaped the identity of SCs as 'Harijans' in the state. Attempts at introducing change were largely limited to Sanskritisation, and the SCs continued to remain politically backward throughout the state. It was only in the 1940s, influenced by the ideas of Dr. Ambedkar, that a small section of the Scheduled Caste population in parts of the state rejected its earlier status and identity, and began to use politics as a means to achieve an equal position in the Indian polity. Moreover, in the post-independence period, apart from a brief phase in the 1960s, it was only in the 1980s that a radical caste consciousness arose in U.P., leading to the formation of the BSP which attempted to create a new identity and political consciousness. Hence, the SC movement in U.P. lacks the depth, intensity, and maturity which characterize the movements in Western India.

Scheduled Castes Movement and Protests in the Colonial Period

In contrast to parts of western India which came under the influence of Babasaheb Ambedkar, U.P. did not experience any large scale anti-caste movement during the colonial period which resulted in delayed development of political consciousness among SCs in the state. The caste structure in the north Indian plains differs fundamentally from that of southern and western India. Historically, anti-Brahminism seems to have developed in the latter regions due to their steep and discontinuous traditional social hierarchies which were almost tyrannical in some parts. Regions with a relatively higher proportion of twice-born castes, having more gradual and continuous hierarchies leading to a less oppressive structure such as in the north Indian plains, seem to have been less susceptible to horizontal mobilization from below, comprising ritually deprived castes seeking opportunities to improve their status and political power. The reasons lie in the rigid and unchanging character of the social structure of the society U.P. The lack of Scheduled Caste movement in the U.P. plains meant the absence of any widespread anti-caste ideology and the passive acceptance of the unequal social and political system of Manubadi Caste system. The anti-colonial movement in U.P. came under the leadership of Mahatma Gandhi while in Maharashtra, though the Congress played an important role, it was profoundly influenced by Dr. Ambedkar. In the United Provinces, both during the Kisan Sabha agitation in 1920-21 and the Civil Disobedience and rent campaigns in 1930-31, low caste tenants and labourers participated in large numbers and even produced an SC leader, Pasi Madari. However, once the movement acquired a degree of autonomy producing peasant leaders and incorporating some of the basic contradictions of Indian society - such as the unequal caste/class hierarchy, the leadership made a conscious effort to separate the 'political' and 'social issues' and called off the movements.

The Scheduled Castes Movement and Protests during Post-Independence in Uttar Pradesh

The formation of RPI in 1958 inaugurated a new and separatist phase in the S.C. movement in U.P., but it proved to be short-lived. The reasons for the brief existence of the RPI and its failure to mobilize the SCs in U.P. lie both within the S.C. community and the nature of the U.P. society and politics during this period. Three major factors were - lack of strong leadership, divisions among the leadership over the strategy to be followed and the ability of the Congress as a broad-based dominant party to attract S.C. votes

The Chamars/Jatavas formed the small educated urban elite who had taken the lead in mobilizing the S.C. community and providing leadership. They were disliked and feared by the other groups lower in the *jati* hierarchy, and lacking a strong leader they failed to unite the political party. Moreover, the leaders were divided regarding the relationship of the Scheduled Caste population with the Congress Party and the Hindu caste community as a whole. The issue was again that of separation versus integration. Studies of various districts show the existence of two main groups the Congress conservatives and the RPI politicians.

Hence, while accepting their SC status and sharing the socio-economic goals of their caste brothers, they preferred to co-operate with the Congress and oppose the RPI. In contrast, the leaders of the RPI felt that a separate political party served the interests of the community better. They tried to use their political positions in the local government or state legislature to further the economic and political interests of the Scheduled Caste population and to raise awareness and a district sense of identity within the community. Moreover, although the RPI had two clear goals to defeat the 'Brahmin' congress party and improve the condition of the Scheduled Caste population – its leaders were divided over the methods to be used, a good example is the issue of reservation. The moderates thought it necessary to continue the policy of protective discrimination for some time in order to help the Scheduled Caste population improve their position in Indian society, and believed they were dependent upon the larger society for their betterment. Electoral data show that the radicals were right about reservation not helping the RPI. Out of a total of 89 reserved Assembly seats in U.P. in the 1962, 1967 and 1969 Assembly elections, the Congress obtained 55, 47 and 46 seat getting 61.80 percent, 55.81 percent and 52.69 percent of the votes respectively, while the RPI obtained 1 seat in 1962, 1 in 1967 and none in 1969, which was barely 1.12 percent of the votes (**Singh and Bose, 1985: 105**)

Finally, the existing power structure in U.P. particularly in the rural areas, in the first two decades after independence, did not allow any space for the RPI to become a strong force, and it remained a marginal party.

The Scheduled Castes Movement and Protests in the Bahujan Party Phase:- The fall of the SP-BSP coalition in June 1995 inaugurated a new Bahujan Phase of the Dalit Movement in which two contradictory mobilisational trends are visible: coalition-building with upper-caste parties and a deepening of the movement at the grassroots level. These have, in the short term, affected the 1996 Lok Sabha, October 1996 State Assembly, and the 1998 Lok Sabha Elections, and in the longer term are of importance to the Dalit Movement (**Pai, 2000: 280**).

First, the BSP leadership, hostile to the SP, in its desire and impatience to capture power moved politically closer to the upper caste parties - Congress and the BJP-making it central to any coalition formed in the state, leading to 'Dalitisation' of the UP politics (*The Hindustan Times*, 1995). This decision marked its conversion from a movement to a party led by an opportunities leadership. In June 1995, the Congress welcomed the decision by the BSP to withdraw support to the SP-BSP coalition but was not keen to support a BSP government. The BJP, in contrast, immediately offered support as it hoped, and a government was formed in June 1995 under the leadership of Mayawati. Although the formation of a Dalit government was an important landmark, due to constant friction between the two parties, it lasted only until 17 December 1995. During this period, the BSP was deeply divided over the leadership's decision and its main support base - Chamars and Pasis - were unhappy as the party laws in the hands of OBCs, mainly the Kurmis who are supporters of the BJP (*The Economic Times*, 1995).

Conclusion: - In India, the people belonging to the Scheduled Castes or the ex-untouchables have been struggling for centuries to free themselves from the stigmatized caste (untouchable) identity ascribed to them in the *Manubadi* caste hierarchy. Their struggle was directed against the various forms of injustice and exploitation. Though the efforts to elevate them from their inhuman condition and protect their self-respect and dignity are very many and sustained over centuries, the numerous types of socio-economic disabilities that they suffer from and the social stigma attached to their untouchable identity. The Hindu social system divides the people into inferior and superior castes and accords them lower and higher statuses respectively. It divides the Hindus into five major caste groups Brahmins, Kshatriyas, Vaishyas, Shudras and Anti- Shudras or untouchables. The Brahmins at the top followed by the Kshatriyas, Vaishyas, Shudras, and Anti-Shudras or untouchables. June 1995 inaugurated a new Bahujan phase of the Dalit movement in which two contradictory mobilization trends are visible: coalition building with upper caste parties and a deepening of the movement at the grass root levels. The BSP leaders were particularly keen to implement their programme of Dalit upliftment, when in power. Mayawati had pursued Dalit oriented policies in the field of education, social welfare

employment generation, and health. This era is also giving rise to a number of protests by Dalits at the grassroots.

Reference

- i. Zelliott, E. *From Untouchable to Dalit: Essays on Ambedkar Movement*. New Delhi: Manohar 1992. Second ed. 1996 [G]
- ii. Murugkar, L. *Dalit Panther Movement in Maharashtra: a Sociological Appraisal*. Bombay: Popular Prakashan 1991.
- iii. Ambedkar, B.R. *Annihilation of Caste, with a reply to 'Mahatma' Gandhi*. New ed. [1st ed. 1936, 2nd 1937, 3rd 1944.] Bangalore: Dalit Sahitya Akademi 1987
- iv. Sachchidananda *Research of Scheduled Castes with Special Reference to Change - A Trend Report in ICSSR Survey of Research in Sociology and Social Anthropology*. Bombay: Popular Prakashan 1974
- v. Guru, G. *Dalit Cultural Movement and the Dialectics of Dalit Politics in Maharashtra*. Mumbai: Vikas Adhyayan Kendra 1997/8
- vi. Guru, G. *Dalit movement in mainstream Sociology*, EPW 3 April 1993: 570-73 [G]
- vii. Bhoite, M. & A. *The Dalit Sahitya Movement in Maharashtra: A Sociological Analysis*, *Sociological Bulletin* 26, 1977: 60-75
- viii. Mohan, P.E. *Scheduled Castes: History of Elevation, Tamil Nadu, 1900-1955 [Useful study of early stages by historian. AdiDravida: 46-9]*. Madras: New Era 1993
- ix. Shah, V.P. (ed.) *Removal of Untouchability*. Ahmedabad: Sociology Department, Gujarat University 1980
- x. Lynch, O. "Political Mobilization and Ethnicity among the Adi-Dravidas in a Bombay Slum", *Economic and Political Weekly* IX, 39, 1974: 1657-68
- xi. Mathew, J. *Ideology, Protest and Social Mobility: Case Study of Mahars and Pulayas*. New Delhi: Inter-India 1986
- xii. Patwardhan, S. *Change among India's Harijans. Maharashtra - a Case Study*. New Delhi: Orient Longmans 1973
- xiii. Rao, M. S. *Social Movements and Social Transformation: a Study of Two Backward Classes Movements in India [Ahir & Irava]*. Delhi: McMillan 1979
- xiv. Hardgrave, R. L. *The Nadars of Tamil Nadu*. Berkeley: University of California Press 1969 Bombay: OUP.